

THE IMPORTANCE OF ECOTOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article presents the advantages and disadvantages of ecotourism in Uzbekistan. Famous for its legendary history and Silk Road heritage, our beautiful country, Uzbekistan, has another unique treasure, its attractive nature. Ecotourism in Uzbekistan is one of the growing fields that can attract visitors with its beautiful nature. Along with the great potential of ecotourism, there are also some problems and difficulties. The source of many tourists' visits to Uzbekistan is the passage of the Silk Road. It is not enough for us, which means we should never give up working on tourism development. I have explained it better below.

Keywords: Silk Road heritage, tourism, ecotourism, environment, development.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda ekoturizmning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari ko'rsatilgan. Afsonaviy tarixi va Ipak yo'li merosi bilan mashhur bo'lgan go'zal yurtimiz O'zbekiston yana bir noyob xazinaga, jozibali tabiatiga ega. O'zbekistonda ekoturizm o'zining go'zal tabiati bilan sayyohlarni o'ziga jalb eta oladigan rivojlanayotgan sohalardan biridir. Ekoturizmning katta salohiyati bilan bir qatorda bir qator muammo va qiyinchiliklar ham mavjud. O'zbekistonga ko'plab sayyohlar kelishining manbai Ipak yo'lining o'tish joyidir. Bu biz uchun yetarli emas, demak, turizmni rivojlantirish ustida ishlashdan hech qachon voz kechmasligimiz kerak. Bu haqda quyida yaxshiroq tushuntirdim.

Kalit so'zlar: Ipak yo'li merosi, turizm, ekoturizm, atrof-muhit, rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены преимущества и недостатки экотуризма в Узбекистане. Наша прекрасная страна Узбекистан, известная своей легендарной историей и наследием Шелкового пути, имеет еще одно уникальное сокровище – привлекательную природу. Экотуризм в Узбекистане является одной из развивающихся областей, которая может привлечь посетителей своей красотой природы. Наряду с большим потенциалом экотуризма существуют также некоторые проблемы и трудности. Источником посещения Узбекистана многими туристами является прохождение Шелкового пути. Нам этого недостаточно, а значит, мы никогда не должны отказываться от работы по развитию туризма. Я объяснил об этом лучше ниже.

Ключевые слова: наследие Шелкового пути, туризм, экотуризм, окружающая среда, развитие.

Introduction

“Ecotourism is not a new phenomenon, it has been known, at least in Europe, since the 1970s” (Sattarova Z, 2024). Ecotourism is defined as “responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment, sustains the wellbeing of local people and involves interpretation and education” (International Ecotourism Society, 2015). According to the sources, in the 1980s ecotourism was more well-known but it was born in 1960 as a consequence of problems with nature. Ecotourism is one of the essential types of tourism. The goal is to educate tourists about conservation efforts while offering them the chance to explore nature. This paper provides types of tourism, effects of ecotourism on environment.

Nowadays, ecotourism has become one of the tourism activities preferred by the tourist. Ecotourism gives people a chance to see the amazing beauty of our world while advocating for wildlife conservation and renewable practices.

Discussions: One of the Most Essential Types of Tourism

Ecotourism is one of the most beneficial forms of tourism in the world. Ecotourism increases people's attitude to nature, the ability to understand between cultures, allows to discover new sites and travel to different unusual places. According to the source, as of February 2023: “81% of travelers worldwide believe that ecotourism is important, so it shows that ecotourism is also financially beneficial for all of the world”. It is excellent for not only financial side but also mental and physical health, reduce stress by spending time in nature and engaging in physical activities with trees, sounds of birds and fresh air. If we improve and focus on ecotourism in Uzbekistan it will be new progress and innovation for traveler. There are 2 types of benefits: it is for travelers and environments. Benefits for travelers is unique experience, connection with nature, opportunities of doing outside activity that wildlife watching observing animals in their natural habitat, such as birdwatching, gorilla trekking, connection between animals, hiking, sustainable lodging.

Environmental awareness: Ecotourism raises awareness regarding environmental issues and inspires travelers to become stewards of the planets. Therefore, by choosing ecotourism, travelers can contribute directly to conservation efforts, save the environment and minimize environmental impacts, such as reducing waste, conserving water and energy, and protecting wildlife habitats.

High Stage of Ecotourism Development

Ecotourism is growing rapidly day by day. “The global ecotourism market size was estimated at USD 195.9 billion and it is expected to attain around USD 656.19 billion by 2032, expanding at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 12.90% over the forecast period 2023 to 2032” (Precedence Research, 2022). “Ecotourism contains four basic elements. First, it means traveling or moving from one destination to another. However, the action should be not harmful to the environment. The focus should be directed to experience to natural destinations. Such areas can offer the best view coming across to natural attractions” (Ceballos-Lascurain, 1990). “Ecotourism is traveling mostly to developing countries especially undisturbed places in the purpose of learning, pleasure or volunteer assistance” (Swanson, 1992). “This should not limit the general meaning of nature-based tourism, since it can rejuvenate the area. In this case with the help of human activity environment can be contributed and local people will have benefit. Next, ecotourism can influence on increasing concern globally on disappearing ecosystems and different cultures” (Kutay, 1990). “Finally, this type of tourism is contribution to sustainable future” (O'Neill, 1991). All these four elements of ecotourism are based on the educative motif. Eco-friendly activities are an important aspect of ecotourism, and they can help travelers minimize their impact on the environment while also enjoying their destinations. 80% of travelers traveled in 2023 as ecotourist. This is an example of development of ecotourism. Nowadays, due to the huge number of factories, air pollution and overwork of people, they are very tired and want to relax, travel in nature and breathe the fresh air. In addition, as ecotourism activities become more too popular over the world, it can lead to the construction of new infrastructure to accommodate more visitors in Uzbekistan.

Bilateral ecotourism

Ecotourism has also negative impacts in some cases. “Although ecotourism has many examples where it has had a positive impact on the environment, negative environment fallout may occur such as over consumption of natural resources, disruption of wildlife and human congestion in natural area through the increase of ecotourists” (Herbig et al., 1997). Although, travelers think that by visit to natural places for conservation and protection natural places as ecotourist, we are saving the environment. However, they do not think about the negative impacts, such as the possibility of harming the animal world, disturbing indigenous people. Too many tourists can also cause environmental pollution. The more tourists there are, the more chaos there is. For instance, excessive waste, water pollution and overcrowding can have harmful consequences for the environment. According to Lindberg and Enriquez: “55 percents of every tourist dollar spent in developing countries leaks back into developed countries” (1994). It is excellent for government. Why everyone wants to develop the tourism industry? Because of earning money and discover the new culture, language and tradition. How we can reduce negative impacts of tourism? There are a few solutions to minimize disadvantageous effects: educating visitors on the importance of conserving and protecting the nature, using public transportation instead of private transportation in order to take care of environment, increasing of inflation by the price of goods, services and lands. “In order to maximize the positive impacts of ecotourism, local communities must be included in the planning and development of ecotourism projects starting in the early stages. In order to participate fully in the planning process, they must be aware of the impacts and be supportive of the development” (Dr. Iftikhar Hussain, 2022). Furthermore, it is essential that knowledge of local communities. If residents know concern about the natural world, they can teach about it to vacationers.

Conclusion.

Tourism is like a financial warehouse. It provides huge financial support for the state. Therefore, the country can be developed by developing tourism. As tourism develops, as the number of tourists increases, some negative consequences may occur. To reduce these, we can develop “ecotourism” and improve tourist’s relationship with nature. Ecotourists travel in such way that every trip is good for both themselves and the environment. “By ecotourism ecotourists can be motivated to learn more about nature, this is their main goal” (Thampi, 2001). For instance, birdwatching is interesting and pleasant in the name of tourists. During the activity, they can also observe what is happening in nature. It can increase their love for environment. In this article, I wrote about the benefits and drawbacks of ecotourism, what can be achieved through its development, and how it can advantage for government.

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